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Ethics

No animal studies are presented in this manuscript.
No human studies are presented in this manuscript.
No potentially identifiable human images or data is presented in this study.

The Winds of Change are Blowing: Globalization's Impact on Renewable Energy and Environmental Challenges

Umar Nazir¹

ABSTRACT

The present study examines the impact of globalization, financial development, human capital, and carbon emissions on adopting renewable energy sources in Pakistan. The advancement of sustainable energy sources is paramount in tackling worldwide environmental issues. The present investigation aimed to scrutinize the uptake of sustainable energy sources to alleviate ecological concerns, utilizing data obtained from Pakistan over the time frame of 1990 to 2021. The study utilized the robust least squares (RLS) approach for data analysis. The results suggest that globalization favors renewable energy, while financial development, human capital, and carbon emissions demonstrate adverse impacts on renewable energy. The present study suggests several policy recommendations to improve the adoption of renewable energy sources and reduce environmental pollution.

Keywords: Renewable energy demand; Globalization; Financial development; Human capital; Robust least squares; Pakistan.

1. INTRODUCTION

Globalization pertains to the phenomenon wherein there is a heightened level of interconnectivity and integration among various economies, societies, and cultures worldwide. According to Zajda (2023), it has exerted a noteworthy influence in augmenting diverse social identities, including but not limited to spiritual, national, traditional, and environmental identities (Zaman, 2023a). The phenomenon of globalization has drawn focus towards the significance of nuclear-powered energy in guaranteeing energy security on a global scale. In addition, it has recently been identified as a prospective remedy for addressing climate change and attaining objectives related to the transition towards low-carbon energy (Khan, 2023). Assessing the ecological advantages of nuclear fission energy, encompassing enhanced efficacy and digital advancement, constitutes a pivotal facet of this deliberation (Sadiq et al., 2023). The emergence of worldwide interconnectivity has significantly influenced the environmental condition of our planet. In order to tackle this matter, it is imperative to devise and execute efficient policies to foster the adoption of sustainable energy sources (Khan & Imran, 2023). According to Zhang et al. (2023), implementing policies aimed at reducing carbon dioxide emissions and promoting sustainable economic development can substantially contribute to preserving our atmosphere. The integration of financial markets and institutions across national borders, commonly referred to as financial globalization, has been a topic of significant discourse in recent times concerning its potential implications on the environment and climate-related issues (Aqib & Zaman, 2023). The phenomenon of financial globalization has the potential to impact global temperatures by either amplifying or mitigating GHG emissions, as posited by Akadiri & Adebayo (2022).

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Renewable energy sources have recently gained considerable attention due to their capacity to mitigate carbon emissions and their favourable ecological outcomes. Expanding sustainable energy sources is widely regarded as a crucial catalyst for the shift towards a more sustainable and low-carbon future, which aligns with globalization's objectives (Jahanger et al., 2022). Numerous nations across the globe are endeavoring to augment their renewable energy generation capabilities via monetary outlays, technological innovations, and economic strategies. The reason for this is that traditional energy sources, which release significant quantities of carbon, are a contributing factor to the phenomenon of climate change. The adoption of renewable energy sources is imperative in order to address the issue of global warming and ensure climate stability. The research conducted by Yi et al. (2023) offers significant insights for policymakers to encourage the adoption of renewable energy sources. The study recommends augmenting investments and streamlining technology transfer processes in nations with substantial renewable energy consumption. The era of globalization has resulted in substantial environmental degradation due to the rise in global production and population. Hence, the employment of low-carbon energy resources is imperative for advancing humanity and preserving the planet's ecological balance. According to Yang and Song (2023), advancing energy efficiency is crucial to addressing climate change and mitigating emissions. Incorporating eco-friendly energy technologies is pivotal in mitigating carbon intensity and advancing environmental sustainability. According to Lee et al. (2023), using renewable energy sources can reduce energy intensity, optimize energy systems, and upgrade industrial structures, thereby contributing to the development of a more sustainable and environmentally friendly energy system.

The term "human capital" pertains to a distinct aspect of human abilities, including the competencies, knowledge, and aptitudes individuals possess (Acheampong et al. 2023, Tanweer et al. 2023). The domain of human abilities encompasses physical and cognitive proficiencies and self-regulatory and nurturing competencies, as posited by England and Folbre (2023). The significance of human capital in fostering economic growth and sustainability through mitigating carbon emissions is noteworthy. Through education and training, individuals can devise inventive solutions, such as labour-added technology, that can concurrently promote economic and environmental sustainability. According to Aqib and Zaman (2023), prioritizing investment in human capital is essential for establishing a sustainable future that promotes prosperity while mitigating adverse environmental effects. Human capital can facilitate green technology adoption, which is considered a crucial factor in promoting environmental efficiency. This perspective is based on the concept of endogenous growth. Enhancing human capital via education and training has the potential to promote the alignment of environmental efficiency. Supplementing these endeavors with bolstered environmental regulations can be potent (Appiah-Twum & Long, 2023). The utilization of human capital has played a significant role in the intricate nature of emissions. This, coupled with the utilization of fossil fuels driven by industrialization, has impeded the attainment of mitigation objectives. According to Sarkodie et al. (2020), there is a pressing need for increased investment in human capital, specifically in education and training, to foster innovative solutions that can effectively mitigate carbon emissions and facilitate sustainable industrialization.

The task of reconciling economic expansion and financial advancement with the safeguarding of the environment is a crucial global predicament that societies and individuals confront. The enhancement of general well-being is contingent upon economic expansion and commensurate financial advancement (Zaman, 2023b). It is feasible to concurrently pursue economic and financial advancement while prioritizing safeguarding the environment. The aforementioned statement highlights the imperative need for the active participation of public authorities, financial institutions, producers, and individuals responsible for making decisions, producing goods, and engaging in consumption practices that prioritize environmental consciousness. According to Acar et al. (2023), it is possible to attain economic and financial progress while upholding environmental sustainability through this approach. The correlation between financial development and economic advancement is a widely acknowledged phenomenon. However, it is important to note that such progress may also result in environmental deterioration, characterized by amplified energy utilization and carbon emissions. The imperative to balance economic growth and environmental sustainability underscores the need to devise strategies that effectively counteract the detrimental effects of financial progress on the natural world (Tahir et al., 2021). Although financial development holds significance for economic growth, it may not be adequate for a sustainable shift towards cleaner energy sources in the long run. According to Saadaoui (2022), there is a pressing need for significant alterations to be made to the financial system in order to facilitate the replacement of polluting energy sources with clean ones. This is a crucial step towards tackling environmental issues and promoting sustainable economic development.

Pakistan encounters several obstacles in achieving environmental sustainability through implementing renewable energy generation (REG). The challenges above emanate from the facilitators and inhibitors of REG advancement. Through a comprehensive examination of various aspects, it has been determined that the principal obstacles to the development of REG in Pakistan are the insufficiency of effective governance, restricted adoption of renewable energy, and insufficient energy policies implemented by the government. The development of REG is influenced by various factors such as the availability of ample

resources, the method of power production, the demand for renewable energy, the investment climate for renewable energy projects, the financial benefits of such projects, the environmental impact, and the level of public acceptance. These factors are considered crucial drivers of REG development. The foremost obstacle to the development of REG in Pakistan is inadequate governance, whereas the environmental ramifications are deemed the least consequential. The development of REG is primarily motivated by public acceptance, whereas inadequate governance represents a significant obstacle. The study conducted by Fatima et al. (2021) highlights the significance of efficient governance and policies that promote the integration of renewable energy sources and encourage investment in Pakistan. This is crucial in achieving sustainable energy production in the country.

The present study aims to address pertinent research questions regarding Pakistan's economy regarding renewable energy. The following research questions have been formulated for investigation:

- I. How do globalization, financial development, human capital, and carbon emissions impact Pakistan's adoption and utilization of renewable energy sources?
- II. How has adopting renewable energy sources evolved in Pakistan from 1990 to 2021?
- III. What policy recommendations can be proposed to enhance the utilization of renewable energy sources and mitigate environmental pollution in Pakistan?

To effectively address these research questions, the study has established the following objectives:

1. To comprehensively examine the effects of globalization, financial development, human capital, and carbon emissions on Pakistan's adoption and utilization of renewable energy sources. This objective seeks to analyze the individual contributions of these factors to the renewable energy sector in the country.
2. To conduct a thorough analysis of the trends and patterns in the adoption of renewable energy sources in Pakistan. This objective intends to provide insights into the historical progression of renewable energy utilization and its corresponding implications for sustainable development.
3. To propose policy recommendations to promote the effective utilization of renewable energy sources and address environmental pollution in Pakistan. This objective seeks to offer actionable measures that can be implemented to advance the transition towards a low-carbon economy and mitigate environmental challenges.

The abovementioned objectives will be evaluated using the RLS regression methodology. This statistical approach is expected to yield reliable estimations of parameters, thereby facilitating the deduction of well-founded policy implications for the economy of Pakistan as it endeavors to achieve its decarbonization goals. The study aims to contribute valuably to developing effective strategies for sustainable energy and environmental preservation in Pakistan by utilizing empirical evidence and rigorous analysis.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The pressing necessity to tackle environmental issues has propelled renewable energy to the forefront of global discourse. The present literature review focuses on the particular context of Pakistan, scrutinizing the impact of globalization, financial development, and human capital on the uptake and application of renewable energy sources. This review aims to elucidate the potential pathways for sustainable energy transition in Pakistan by examining the interplay between various factors. This will contribute to the broader understanding of the role of renewable energy in mitigating environmental concerns. This review aims to provide policy recommendations for promoting renewable energy deployment and environmental sustainability in Pakistan by analyzing existing research and empirical evidence. The study by Zhu (2023) aimed to investigate the impact of human capital and environmental protection on achieving sustainable development goals (SDGs) in China over a time frame of 33 years, from 1986 to 2019. The research produced results suggesting that allocating resources towards human capital and environmental conservation development can decrease carbon emissions and promote the achievement of SDGs. On the contrary, it has been observed that there exists a positive correlation between economic and population growth and the escalation of carbon emissions. The findings above offer significant perspectives for decision-makers in China to develop sustainable development strategies. Abbas et al. (2023) conducted a study to identify the primary factors driving environmental innovation across 29 OECD member countries over 26 years from 1993 to 2019. The findings indicate that adopting environmental taxation, carbon pricing measures, and encouraging private enterprise investment in advancing renewable energy are essential for facilitating ecological innovation. The research findings suggest that attaining sustainable development goals requires the implementation of rigorous policy regulations at the regional level and facilitating financial sector growth. Ramzan et al. (2023a) surveyed the influence of government revenues, debts, and renewable energy on attaining environmental neutrality in the United States between the first quarter of 1990 and the fourth quarter of 2020. The findings suggest a correlation between the utilization of sustainable energy sources and the extent of financial capital concerning the ecological footprint. Additionally, the environmental footprint is associated with tax revenues and

government debts. The research recommends adopting tax reform measures to encourage the allocation of resources towards renewable energy sources. This approach would facilitate the advancement of environmental sustainability and contribute to achieving the United Nations' SDGs. The study by Jahanger et al. (2023) examined the potential of natural energy sources in mitigating greenhouse gas emissions and attaining the SDGs in the leading ten manufacturing nations. This research investigated the influence of renewable energy on achieving carbon neutrality between 1990 and 2020. The findings indicate noteworthy decreases in emissions within these nations due to the implementation of sustainable energy alternatives. Policymakers can utilize the results of this study to formulate efficacious approaches towards attaining carbon neutrality.

The study by Shayanmehr et al. (2023) aimed to assess the effects of ecological sustainability policies on the ecological footprint (EFP) of the primary renewable energy consumers between 1994 and 2018. The investigation additionally examined the function of environmental taxation. The findings indicate that implementing environmental taxes and utilizing renewable energy sources substantially contribute to mitigating the ecological footprint, especially in nations with high pollution levels. Implementing environmental taxation incentivizes the adoption of sustainable energy sources that are less harmful to the environment. The study revealed that economic globalization and human capital adversely affect the ecological footprint, whereas GDP and non-renewable energy consumption exacerbate it. It is recommended that policymakers implement an increase in environmental taxation and allocate resources towards sustainable energy sources to address environmental degradation. Ramzan et al. (2023b) investigated the effects of green innovation and financial globalization on the environment and energy transition in the United Kingdom from 1995 to 2020. The findings suggest that a one-way causal relationship exists among green innovation, financial globalization, environmental sustainability, and energy transition. The factors above are instrumental in mitigating environmental degradation and facilitating the transition towards sustainable energy. The study revealed that GDP and energy consumption have been identified as factors that impede the transition to sustainable energy and contribute to environmental degradation. The research emphasizes the significance of enforcing rigorous environmental policies and promoting the uptake of energy-efficient innovations in both the conventional industrial and financial domains to tackle these issues. The study conducted by Gangopadhyay et al. (2023) examined the impact of REC, globalization, trade, and GDP on carbon emissions in the United States over the period spanning from 1970 to 2019. The results indicate a negative correlation between REC and carbon emission in all quantiles. In contrast, the connection between globalization and carbon emissions is positive. The study revealed no statistically significant impact of trade on CO₂ emissions. Additionally, the influence of GDP on CO₂ emissions was found to be positive only at lower quantiles. The research suggests a dynamic policy framework that revolves around the SDGs to alleviate the impacts of climate change and encourage the adoption of clean energy consumption within the United States. Ali et al. (2023) investigated the interrelationship among economic growth, globalization, REC and non-REC in South America over 25 years, from 1995 to 2020, focusing on the environmental aspect. The research indicates a positive correlation between economic growth and environmental pollution. At the same time, using RE sources is associated with reducing pollution levels, both in the short and long run. The impact of economic globalization on environmental pollution is beneficial over an extended period. However, social globalization and the moderating influence of political globalization on RE sources contribute to improving environmental quality in the long run. The research emphasizes prospective policy interventions to alleviate environmental contamination in South America. The study conducted by Yang et al. (2022) aimed to examine the interplay between carbon emissions, financial development, population, green technology innovation, energy consumption, and employment rate in China over a period spanning from 1980 to 2019. The findings indicate that implementing green technology innovation and financial development exerts a noteworthy influence on preserving the environment over an extended period. By contrast, the correlation between environmental protection and energy consumption and the employment rate was comparatively weaker. Nonetheless, the effectiveness of green technology innovation in mitigating environmental degradation was not substantiated in the immediate term. The research suggests the implementation of a sturdy financial infrastructure to promote enduring viability. Additionally, integrating eco-friendly technologies across various sectors can augment GHG emissions reduction. Implementing stringent environmental policies can effectively steer the financial and conventional industrial domains towards the assimilation of energy-efficient technologies within China.

The study by Chien (2022) suggests significant negative correlations between CO₂ emissions in China and variables such as REP, energy import, and REC. On the other hand, it was discovered that there exist positive associations between CO₂ emissions and GDP, inflation, and FDI. The research suggests implementing policies in China that facilitate generating and utilizing sustainable energy sources as a viable strategy to mitigate carbon emissions significantly. The study conducted by Yao et al. (2023) investigated the correlation between the increase in graduate students, the development of inventive human resources, and the level of green total factor productivity (GTFP) in China from 2005 to 2018. The findings indicate that the growth of GTFP is driven by the increase in enrollment of graduate students and the existence of inventive human capital. However, the benefits of such factors tend to decrease over time. According to the research findings, to facilitate the growth of Graduate Technology Entrepreneurship in China, it is recommended to focus on promoting the expansion of graduate students, optimizing enrollment

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structures, and establishing a conducive environment for social innovation. The study conducted by Dada et al. (2023) substantiated the influence of the shadow economy, financial development, economic growth, trade openness, and urbanization on environmental sustainability across 30 African nations between 1991 and 2017. The findings indicate that a shadow economy, economic expansion, and urbanization positively correlate with the intensification of the ecological footprint. Conversely, trade openness is observed to have a negative correlation with the ecological footprint. The research indicates that a robust financial system has the potential to mitigate the adverse effects of the shadow economy on ecological deterioration. A reciprocal relationship has been identified between the ecological footprint and the shadow economy, bio-capacity and the shadow economy, and financial development. The research emphasizes the policy implications of the findings above for African economies. The study by Yousaf & Fazal (2022) examined the effects of sustainable energy, technology adoption, green finance, and economic growth on environmental sustainability in China. The research utilized data spanning from 1990 to 2020. The research has revealed that in China, environmental sustainability is positively influenced by REP, REC, technology adoption, green finance, and economic growth. The discoveries above offer significant perspectives for policymakers in formulating regulations to enhance environmental sustainability in China via implementing sustainable energy, green finance, and technology adoption. The study conducted by Hussain & Shahid (2021) investigated the correlation between green energy, economic growth, and environmental degradation in China. The research utilized data spanning from 1981 to 2018. The research indicates that in China, green energy displays an inverse relationship with environmental degradation and economic growth, whereas inflation is positively associated with environmental degradation. The research suggests adopting sustainable energy sources as a viable strategy for mitigating the adverse effects of ecological deterioration in China.

The study conducted by Abdul et al. (2022) indicates that implementing renewable energy sources can aid in reducing environmental degradation in China. Conversely, the inflow of foreign remittances, the process of globalization, the advancement of financial development, and the expansion of economic growth may contribute to exacerbating environmental deterioration. The findings suggest that using sustainable energy resources can facilitate China's objectives of attaining self-sufficiency in energy and mitigating the impacts of climate change. Nonetheless, the Chinese government must undertake tangible measures to mitigate CO₂ emissions while fostering social welfare and sustainability. The authors of the study conducted by He et al. (2022) indicate that using RE and the revenue generated from oil decreases GHGs, thereby promoting ecological sustainability. On the contrary, the relationship between economic growth and natural resources and their impact on GHG emissions is such that it impedes the attainment of environmental sustainability. The discoveries above present prospective resolutions for augmenting the environmental sustainability of China. The authors Raihan et al. (2023) put forth a set of policy recommendations to achieve environmental sustainability in Indonesia by reducing carbon emissions. The recommendations highlight the significance of a low-carbon economy, greater adoption of RE, financial backing for technological innovations, and the conservation of Indonesia's forests. The study by Tzeremes et al. (2023) examined the correlation among energy transition, economic growth, CO₂ emissions, and ICT in BRICS nations from 2000 to 2017. The research indicates that carbon emissions exhibit a favourable effect on the energy transition process, while augmented energy transition consumption is linked to economic expansion. ICT has also been recognized as a crucial element in enabling the shift towards sustainable energy and mitigating environmental issues. The results of this study indicate that providing government assistance towards the development of ICT is imperative in promoting the adoption of sustainable energy sources and facilitating the transition towards sustainable energy systems in BRICS nations. The study conducted by Raihan & Tuspekova (2023) investigated the potential impact of economic growth, renewable energy consumption, technological innovation, and forest management on the reduction of carbon emissions in Kazakhstan during the period spanning from 1990 to 2020. The research indicates a positive correlation between the increase in economic growth and the utilization of RE sources with the rise in CO₂ emissions. Conversely, the reduction of CO₂ emissions is attributed to technological advancements and effective forest management practices. The results underscore the significance of attaining environmental sustainability in Kazakhstan through sustainable economic growth, technological progress, and forest conservation.

Based on the stated literature review, the study formed the following research hypotheses, i.e.,

H1: Globalization positively impacts the adoption and utilization of renewable energy sources in Pakistan.

H2: Financial development, human capital, and carbon emissions negatively influence the adoption and utilization of renewable energy sources in Pakistan.

H3: The adoption of renewable energy sources has increased in Pakistan, indicating progress in addressing environmental challenges.

The present study makes a scholarly contribution by investigating the impact of globalization, financial development, human capital, and carbon emissions on adopting REC in Pakistan. Prior research has investigated certain factors in isolation; however, there exists a need for more scholarly inquiry into the collective impact of these factors on the uptake of renewable energy in

Pakistan. Additionally, the present research addresses a temporal void by employing data that covers more than thirty years, furnishing a thorough examination of the enduring patterns and fluctuations. The utilization of the RLS technique in this study elevates the methodological precision and veracity of the results. The study's originality stems from its comprehensive methodology, which considers various factors and their interconnectedness. Additionally, the study provides customized policy suggestions that address Pakistan's unique obstacles and prospects in augmenting its use of renewable energy and reducing environmental contamination.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present research endeavors to examine the correlation between renewable energy and a group of autonomous factors within the framework of Pakistan. The study employs yearly time series data covering the period from 1990 to 2021. The World Development Indicators (WDI) published by the World Bank (2023) were utilised to gather data on renewable energy (RE), financial development (FD), per capita GDP (GDP), globalization (GLO), carbon emissions (CO₂), and human capital (HC). Table 1 presents a comprehensive list of variables for quick and easy reference.

Table 1: List of Variables

Symbol	Variables description	Units of measurement
RE	Renewable energy	% of total final energy consumption
HC	Human capital	Total labor force
FD	Financial development	Bank credit to private sector as % of GDP
GLO	Globalization	Trade (% of GDP)
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide emission	Metric tons per capita
GDP	GDP per capita	GDP per capita (constant 2015 US\$)

Source: World Bank (2022).

Robust least squares (RLS) estimation methods accommodate possible outliers or influential observations in the dataset. M-estimation, S-estimation, and MM estimation techniques provide a higher degree of robustness than the conventional OLS approach, particularly when confronted with substantial outliers or data points that may exert a considerable influence on the outcomes. The robust methods rely on order statistics and distinct weighting schemes to identify outliers and reduce inefficiencies. Huber (1973) introduced M-estimation to derive probability functions for a specified parameter. The S-estimation technique, proposed by Rousseeuw and Yohai (1984), is known for its computational complexity; however, it has demonstrated efficacy in detecting outliers within the independent variables. Yohai (1987) introduced MM estimation, which can detect outliers in independent and dependent variables. The present study utilizes a fusion of S-estimation and M-estimation methodologies to augment the resilience of the analysis. The regression equation used in this study is as follows:

$$\ln(RE)_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln(GLO)_t + \beta_2 \ln(FD)_t + \beta_3 \ln(GDP)_t + \beta_4 \ln(HC)_t + \beta_5 \ln(CO_2)_t + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

In Equation (1), the subscript "t" represents the period from 1990 to 2021. The slope coefficients β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , β_4 , and β_5 . The term ε denotes the residual component of the regression equation.

Zaman (2023c) has introduced the concept of cross-panel techniques, which are a novel approach to assessing a country's actions in response to decisions made by other countries, to advance sustainable objectives. The utilization of CiteScore rankings is a feasible metric that can facilitate a more rigorous assessment of the indexing of scholarly materials, thereby promoting the widespread dissemination of information (Zaman, 2023d). In order to ensure stability and mitigate concerns about fluctuating data, a natural logarithm transformation is implemented on all variables within the time series dataset. The conversion above aids in attaining linearity and mitigating the impact of outliers, which is especially advantageous for variables that demonstrate exponential expansion or asymmetrical distributions. The present study endeavors to offer dependable and resilient insights into the correlation between REC and the chosen independent variables within the framework of Pakistan through the utilization of robust estimation techniques and logarithmic transformations.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 displays the descriptive statistics of the variables. The variable "RE" exhibits a mean value of approximately 3.89, signifying the average level. The dataset exhibits a range of values that extends from 3.74 to 4.06. The standard deviation is relatively low, measuring at 0.09, which implies that the data points are near the mean. The data about the distribution of "RE" exhibits a marginal positive skewness of 0.22, which implies a little inclination towards elevated values and a slight rightward asymmetry. The kurtosis value of 2.18 indicates that the distribution exhibits moderate leptokurtosis or heavy-tailedness.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	RE	FD	GLO	HC	CO2	GDP
Mean	3.886567	3.031648	3.450371	17.74604	-0.365856	6.596411
Median	3.870054	3.103499	3.483141	17.77224	-0.350336	6.591001
Maximum	4.062016	3.358073	3.650640	18.15860	-0.084584	7.390640
Minimum	3.739810	2.686639	3.206867	17.28268	-0.681335	5.848369
Std. Dev.	0.087735	0.218345	0.131778	0.271052	0.154757	0.509668
Skewness	0.224432	-0.307231	-0.261535	-0.242334	-0.148126	0.130341
Kurtosis	2.180856	1.604734	1.840907	1.748033	2.325904	1.514505

Source: Author's estimate.

The variable "FD" exhibits a mean of approximately 3.03, with a range of values spanning from 2.69 to 3.36. The data exhibits moderate variability, as indicated by the standard deviation 0.22. The statistical distribution of "FD" exhibits a slight leftward skewness with a value of -0.31, which suggests a minor deviation from symmetry towards lower values. The kurtosis value of 1.60 indicates that the distribution exhibits moderate leptokurtosis or heavier tails than a normal distribution. The variable denoted as "GLO" exhibits an average value of approximately 3.45, from 3.21 to 3.65. The data exhibits minimal variability, as indicated by the standard deviation of 0.13. The statistical distribution of "GLO" exhibits a minor leftward skewness with a value of -0.26, indicating a subtle deviation from symmetry towards the lower end of the distribution. The kurtosis coefficient of 1.84 suggests that the distribution exhibits a degree of leptokurtosis, indicating that it has tails that are moderately heavier than those of a normal distribution. The variable "HC" exhibits a mean value of approximately 17.75, from 17.28 to 18.16. A standard deviation of 0.27 indicates that the data exhibits moderate variability. The "HC" data distribution exhibits a little leftward skewness with a value of -0.24, which suggests a slight deviation from symmetry towards lower values. The kurtosis coefficient of 1.75 indicates that the distribution exhibits a moderate degree of leptokurtosis or heavy-tailedness. The arithmetic mean of the variable "CO2" is approximately -0.37, exhibiting a range from -0.68 to -0.08. The data exhibit minimal variation, as indicated by the standard deviation of 0.15. The statistical distribution of "CO2" exhibits a little leftward skewness (skewness = -0.15), indicating a slight deviation from symmetry towards the lower end of the distribution. The kurtosis value of 2.33 suggests that the distribution exhibits a leptokurtic characteristic, indicating a heavier tail than a normal distribution. Finally, regarding the variable denoting per capita GDP, the average value is approximately 6.60, with a range spanning from 5.85 to 7.39. The data exhibits moderate variability based on the calculated standard deviation of 0.51. The GDP distribution exhibits a little rightward skewness with a value of 0.13, implying a slight deviation from symmetry towards the upper end of the distribution. The kurtosis value of 1.51 indicates that the distribution exhibits a moderate degree of tail weight. The analysis of Figure 1 reveals that the model's regressors exhibit a clustering pattern around the mean values of their corresponding variables. This trend is particularly noticeable for CO2, human capital, globalization, and economic growth. This implies the potential existence of outliers within the model. Outliers refer to observations that exhibit a substantial deviation from the general trend of the dataset. The existence of outliers can potentially affect the estimation outcomes and the general dependability of the model.

RE vs. Variables (Partialled on Regressors)

Figure 1: Leverage Plots

Source: Author's estimate.

Identifying and remedying outliers is paramount in statistical analysis, as they can distort the observed patterns and relationships within the data. The presence of outliers in a dataset can be attributed to various factors such as inaccuracies in measurement, errors during data entry, or extreme values within the phenomenon under investigation. The appropriate detection and handling of outliers is crucial to ensure the robustness and accuracy of regression analysis. Additional inquiry and rigorous analytical methodologies, such as the RLS technique, may be implemented to account for the possible impact of outliers and enhance the dependability of the model's outcomes. The abovementioned technique has been formulated to mitigate the influence of outliers and give more precise approximations of the associations among variables. In general, the existence of outliers among the model's regressors, as indicated by Figure 1, underscores the importance of thorough deliberation and resilient analysis methods to guarantee the credibility of the regression outcomes. The model has undergone various outlier detection tests, as indicated in Figure 2. The findings suggest that there are outliers present within the dataset. Individuals join organizations with specific needs, skills, and expectations, seeking a work environment that allows them to utilize their abilities to fulfill those needs. When organizations can offer such opportunities, it enhances the likelihood of increasing employee commitment. In this study, the researcher investigated the commitment and attitude of employees at the University. The findings regarding employees' commitment and attitude are depicted in Figure 1.

Influence Statistics

Figure 2: Influence Statistics

Source: Author's estimate.

The R Student test has identified the presence of two outliers. The R Student test evaluates individual observations' impact on a regression model's estimated coefficients. The identification of outliers through this test indicates that these particular observations substantially influence the estimated associations among the variables. An outlier has been identified through the employment of the Hat matrix test. The Hat matrix is a statistical tool utilized to quantify the impact of individual observations on the estimated values of the regression model. The identification of an outlier through this test indicates that the corresponding observation significantly impacts the predicted values of the model. According to the DFFITS test, two observations have been identified as outliers. The DFFITS metric gauges the impact of individual observations on the anticipated outcomes while considering the standard error of the estimated values. The identification of outliers through this test signifies observations that exert a substantial influence on the anticipated values of the model. Finally, the COVRATIO test has identified five data points that deviate significantly from the rest of the sample, commonly called outliers. The COVRATIO test is a statistical method that evaluates the impact of removing individual observations on the estimated covariance matrix. The identification of outliers through this test indicates the presence of observations that significantly impact the estimated covariance structure of the model. The existence of anomalous observations within the dataset can impact the approximated coefficients, anticipated outcomes, and the general dependability of the regression model. Thoroughly examining and comprehending the characteristics of these outliers and their probable influence on the analysis holds significant importance. Depending on the research objectives, appropriate measures can be implemented, such as using RLS regression methods, data transformation, or excluding outliers if they are considered to have a significant impact or are erroneous. The outcomes of the RLS estimation are displayed in Table 3.

Table 3: RLS Estimates

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
FD	-0.043499	0.013988	-3.109752	0.0019
GLO	0.042268	0.018064	2.339922	0.0193
HC	-0.076393	0.022517	-3.392641	0.0007
CO2	-0.425178	0.032118	-13.23796	0.0000
GDP	-0.008911	0.015338	-0.580996	0.5612
C	5.131835	0.365375	14.04538	0.0000

Robust Statistics			
R-squared	0.836456	Adjusted R-squared	0.805005
Rw-squared	0.995696	Adjust Rw-squared	0.995696
Akaike info criterion	40.02107	Schwarz criterion	51.34389
Deviance	0.001218	Scale	0.006313
Rn-squared statistic	4093.951	Prob(Rn-squared stat.)	0.000000

Non-robust Statistics			
Mean dependent var	3.886567	S.D. dependent var	0.087735
S.E. of regression	0.007558	Sum squared resid	0.001485

The results suggest an inverse correlation between FD and RE, whereby a 1 unit rise in FD is associated with a 0.043 unit decline in RE. In order to mitigate the adverse effects, it is recommended that the government enact measures aimed at facilitating the availability of financial services, allocating resources towards R&D, fostering a range of financial services, enhancing financial literacy, and bolstering sustainable and equitable economic expansion. Conversely, a correlation of a favourable nature exists between globalization (GLO) and RE. The findings suggest a positive correlation exists between globalization and renewable energy, wherein a marginal increase of 1 unit in globalization is linked to a corresponding increase of 0.042 units in RE. The rise of globalization may lead to an upsurge in utilizing sustainable energy sources. In order to augment the utilization of RE, policy measures can prioritize the facilitation of international trade, the attraction of foreign investments, the enhancement of international cooperation, the improvement of infrastructure, and the promotion of cultural exchange. Moreover, the examination demonstrates an inverse correlation between HC and RE. An incremental rise of 1 unit in human capital results in a corresponding reduction of 0.076 unit in RE. In order to mitigate the adverse effects, the government must give precedence to measures such as energy efficiency initiatives, incentives for renewable energy, imposition of carbon taxes, research on clean energy, and promotion of public awareness and education. Likewise, a correlation exists between CO₂ emissions and RE, wherein the former exhibits a negative relationship with the latter. An increase of one unit in CO₂ is associated with a reduction of 0.42 unit in RE. In order to mitigate this adverse correlation, it is imperative to allocate resources towards sustainable energy sources, establish objectives for reducing carbon emissions, endorse energy conservation, enhance public consciousness, and foster international cooperation. Habiba et al. (2022) assert that implementing green technology innovations and the widespread adoption of renewable energy sources are crucial factors in mitigating carbon emissions and realizing sustainable development goals. According to Haldar & Sethi (2022), it is recommended that developing countries promote the growth of internet accessibility and usage, as well as adopt sustainable energy practices and eco-friendly innovations in the telecommunications industry, in order to reduce their environmental impact. The significance of advancing research and development of low-carbon technologies and investing in renewable energy is emphasized by Kirikkaleli et al. (2022), particularly in mitigating reliance on imported nonrenewable energy sources. The study by Xu et al. (2022) establishes that using RE sources is a viable solution to reduce the negative effects on the environment, improve ecological conditions, and promote economic advancement. According to Esquivias et al. (2022), CO₂ emissions are influenced by various factors, including economic growth, population density, and the development of renewable energy technologies. Enhancing environmental sustainability can be achieved through investment in capital, advocacy for adopting RE, and green technology and human capital cultivation. Saqib et al. (2023) emphasize the significance of technological advancements, effective utilization of human resources, and adopting RE sources in mitigating the ecological impact. Kuldasheva & Salahodjaev (2022) emphasize that integrating RE sources is crucial in mitigating carbon emissions and fostering a greener and more sustainable ecosystem. According to the findings depicted in Figure 3, the stability of the model has been evaluated through the utilization of CUSUM (Cumulative Sum) and CUSUM square tests, revealing that the model remains stable at a 5% confidence level.

Figure 3: Model Stability Estimates

Source: Author's estimate.

The CUSUM and CUSUM square tests are statistical methods for evaluating a regression model's constancy throughout a given period. The tests in question evaluate the total sum of the estimated coefficients or their squares to ascertain the presence of significant deviations or structural breaks within the model. The CUSUM and CUSUM square test statistics, remain within the critical bounds at the selected confidence level of 5%. In that case, it indicates that the model is stable and that there are no significant alterations or structural breaks in the association between the variables over time. The statistical significance of the model at a 5% level of significance suggests that the estimated coefficients and their interrelationships exhibit consistency and dependability throughout the analyzed timeframe. The outcome above instills assurance in the authenticity of the regression outcomes and implies that the associations between the independent and reliant variables are consistent and can be trusted for subsequent scrutiny and elucidation. Table 4 displays the VDA estimates, which provide insight into the anticipated fluctuations of renewable energy and other pertinent factors in the forthcoming timeframes. According to the analysis, RE is anticipated to undergo a more substantial decline in the forthcoming period.

Table 4: VDA Estimates

Period	S.E.	RE	FD	GLO	HC	CO2	GDP
1	0.020466	100.0000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
2	0.026668	84.88137	11.10684	0.068104	0.028765	2.229802	1.685117
3	0.029594	76.31653	11.35435	3.286525	0.025821	7.583897	1.432877
4	0.030764	70.74807	10.77383	6.843438	0.460461	9.830995	1.343215
5	0.031096	69.49049	10.63150	7.268237	1.297921	9.904009	1.407847
6	0.031531	68.29623	10.58824	7.104164	2.494078	9.637116	1.880174
7	0.031997	66.78364	10.60512	7.131212	3.539252	9.395113	2.545662
8	0.032290	65.59268	10.60858	7.224444	4.314829	9.229963	3.029502
9	0.032474	65.05528	10.51675	7.288478	4.764322	9.138651	3.236524
10	0.032659	64.94585	10.40798	7.256978	4.993850	9.129005	3.266344

Over ten years, from period 1 (2023) to period 10 (2032), there has been a discernible decreasing trend in the impact of FD on RE. The projected impact for 2024 is estimated to be 11.106%, slightly increasing to 11.354%. The effect above exhibits a gradual decline over time, ultimately reaching a value of 10.407% by 2032. This suggests an anticipated reduction in the influence of financial development on RE over the period under examination. In contrast, the impact of GLO on RE is projected to experience a slight rise in the forthcoming years. It is projected that the impact of globalization will increase from 0.068% to 7.256% by 2032. This implies that globalization is anticipated to result in a corresponding surge in utilizing RE sources. The impact of HC on RE is projected to experience a gradual yet consistent rise in the coming years. While the precise values of the estimates are not specified, the pattern suggests a gradual increase in the influence of human capital on RE. Finally, there is a growing trend in the impact of CO2 emissions on RE. Over the next decade, it is anticipated that the projected impact of CO2 will rise from 2.229% to 9.129%. This suggests that a rise in carbon emissions is associated with a reduction in using RE sources. In light of the VDA estimates outlined in Table 4, it can be deduced that the influence of FD on RE is anticipated to decline. In contrast, the impact of GLO, HC, and carbon emissions on RE is predicted to fluctuate in the forthcoming period. The IRF estimates are presented in Table 5, offering valuable insights into the impact of various factors on RE. The analysis findings reveal that various factors exhibit dual impacts on utilizing RE, encompassing favorable and unfavorable outcomes.

Table 5: IRF Estimates

Period	RE	FD	GLO	HC	CO2	GDP
1	0.020466 (0.00264)	0.000000 (0.00000)	0.000000 (0.00000)	0.000000 (0.00000)	0.000000 (0.00000)	0.000000 (0.00000)
2	0.013595 (0.00476)	-0.008888 (0.00487)	-0.000696 (0.00509)	0.000452 (0.00486)	-0.003982 (0.00440)	-0.003462 (0.00395)
3	0.008044 (0.00529)	-0.004522 (0.00529)	0.005320 (0.00554)	0.000147 (0.00365)	-0.007111 (0.00494)	-0.000752 (0.00427)
4	0.001096 (0.00519)	-0.001589 (0.00516)	0.005999 (0.00523)	-0.002033 (0.00343)	-0.005160 (0.00454)	-0.000404 (0.00441)
5	-0.001531 (0.00477)	0.000912 (0.00502)	0.002347 (0.00417)	-0.002862 (0.00268)	-0.001650 (0.00359)	0.000949 (0.00427)
6	-0.002659 (0.00413)	0.001571 (0.00458)	-0.000592 (0.00343)	-0.003499 (0.00247)	0.000216 (0.00299)	0.002254 (0.00411)
7	-0.002172 (0.00378)	0.001818 (0.00403)	-0.001542 (0.00303)	-0.003382 (0.00247)	0.000611 (0.00252)	0.002715 (0.00391)
8	-0.000415 (0.00357)	0.001427 (0.00336)	-0.001522 (0.00275)	-0.002959 (0.00226)	0.000222 (0.00220)	0.002350 (0.00360)
9	0.001463 (0.00338)	0.000542 (0.00272)	-0.001239 (0.00249)	-0.002292 (0.00191)	-0.000368 (0.00191)	0.001595 (0.00326)
10	0.002582 (0.00316)	-0.000326 (0.00235)	-0.000736 (0.00215)	-0.001738 (0.00166)	-0.000999 (0.00167)	0.000841 (0.00291)

A combination of positive and negative outcomes characterizes the impact of FD on RE. The impact of FD on RE can vary depending on the particular temporal context. The statement above posits that the correlation between FD and RE is intricate and subject to temporal fluctuations. Likewise, globalization exhibits favorable and unfavorable impacts on sustainable energy. The impact of globalization on RE exhibits temporal variation, suggesting a dynamic interplay. The residual variables, which have yet to be explicitly delineated, demonstrate varied impacts on utilizing RE sources. The effects of these factors on RE can be either

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beneficial or detrimental, contingent upon the particular temporal context. Table 5 displays mixed effects, suggesting that the association between the factors above and renewable energy is not uniformly affirmative or adverse. The statement underscores the intricate and ever-changing interplay between the factors above and renewable energy.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The present research investigates the relationship among RE, FD, GLO, HC, carbon emissions, and economic growth in the specific context of Pakistan. The objective is to comprehend the correlation among the variables above, whereby renewable energy is considered the dependent variable, while the rest were explanatory factors. The study's results suggest that several recommendations could be proposed to the government of Pakistan. Initially, providing financial incentives and subsidies has the potential to stimulate the extensive adoption and advancement of renewable energy sources. This measure has the potential to foster a conducive atmosphere for the implementation of sustainable energy initiatives and stimulate capital inflows into the industry. Furthermore, allocating adequate financial resources towards research and development endeavors pertaining to renewable energy technologies is crucial. Promoting such practices can facilitate novel ideas and progressions within the domain, ultimately resulting in enhanced efficacy and economic feasibility of sustainable energy alternatives.

Facilitating global partnerships and coordination in renewable energy initiatives can yield advantageous outcomes. Collaboration with foreign nations, establishments, and entities can be employed to capitalize on the knowledge, exchange optimal methodologies, and expedite the implementation of sustainable energy innovations. It is imperative to allocate resources towards education and training initiatives tailored to cultivate a proficient labor force within the renewable energy industry. Implementing this measure can guarantee the existence of a reservoir of proficient experts possessing the essential expertise and competencies to propel the expansion and durability of the renewable energy sector. The adoption of proficient carbon pricing mechanisms and the establishment of ambitious emission reduction objectives can serve as a motivator for the shift towards more sustainable energy alternatives. Adopting renewable energy alternatives and the reduction of carbon footprint can be incentivized among both industries and individuals. In addition, the incorporation of environmental factors into financial systems has the potential to facilitate sustainable development. The process may entail the integration of environmental risk assessments, green financing mechanisms, and sustainable investment practices within financial institutions and regulatory frameworks.

By adopting the suggested policies and strategies, Pakistan has the potential to bolster its renewable energy industry, curtail carbon emissions, and promote sustainable and equitable economic development.

Ethical approval

Not Applicable.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

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Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

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